

SYNTHESIS IN ACRIDINE SERIES. PART IV. 5-N-SUBSTITUTED
2:4-DIBROMO- AND 2:4-DIBROMO-7-METHOXYACRIDINE

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5-N-substituted amino-2:4-dibromo-7-methoxy and the corresponding demethoxy-acridine derivatives have been described.

Work described in the present communication is in connection with the synthesis of 5-N-substituted 2:4-dibromo-(I) and 2:4-dibromo-7-methoxy-acridine (II) derivatives and these have been obtained by the well-known method (Drozdzov, *J. Gen. Chem.*, 1938, 8, 937; Goodall and Kermack, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1546) consisting of the cyclisation of the amide of the corresponding diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid obtained from the acid chloride of the latter and the necessary amine.

3':5'-Dibromo-(III) and 3':5'-dibromo-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acids (IV), required for the synthesis of (I) and (II), were obtained by Ullmann's condensation of 3:5-dibromoaniline respectively with *o*-chlorobenzoic acid and 2-bromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid. Compounds (III) and (IV) on cyclisation with excess of phosphorus oxychloride afforded 2:4-dibromo- and 2:4-dibromo-7-methoxyacridone respectively, instead of the expected 5-chloroacridine derivatives. Hence, the facile method of obtaining 5-N-substituted acridine derivatives by allowing the corresponding 5-chloroacridine to react with an amine in presence of phenol is not applicable for the synthesis of (I) and (II), described here.

EXPERIMENTAL

3':5'-Dibromo-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid (IV).—A mixture of 2-bromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid (10 g.), 3:5-dibromoaniline (13 g.), fused potassium carbonate (8 g.), *iso*amyl alcohol (50 c.c.) and a trace of copper powder was refluxed for 3 hours at 130-135°. *iso*Amyl alcohol was removed by steam-distillation and the resulting solution after treatment with charcoal was filtered, acidified, and the product was collected and washed with boiling water. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in small plates, m.p. 205-207°, yield 15 g. (Found: Equiv., 395.0; Br, 40.6. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2NBr_2$ requires equiv., 401.0; Br, 39.9%).

The acid chloride was obtained by refluxing a mixture of the above acid (1 g.), thionyl chloride (3 c.c.) and benzene (10 c.c.) and crystallised from benzene-petrol as brown needles, m.p. 161-63°. (Found: Cl, 8.5; Br, 38.7. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2NClBr_2$ requires Cl, 8.4; Br, 38.1%).

Formation of 2:4-Dibromo-7-methoxyacridone.—The above acid (1 g.) and $POCl_3$ (4 c.c.) were heated at 105-110° for 1 hour and the excess of oxychloride was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The residual liquid was decomposed by pouring it over a mixture of ice and ammonia solution, and the product obtained was filtered immediately, washed with a large amount of water and allowed to dry in air.

It was insoluble in benzene and chloroform. It crystallised from boiling glacial acetic acid in yellow powder, m.p. $> 300^\circ$, yield 0.6 g. (Found: Br, 41.1. $C_{14}H_{13}O_2NBr_2$ requires Br, 41.7%).

3':5'-Dibromodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (III) was obtained by the Ullmann condensation of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid with 3:5-dibromoaniline. It crystallised from acetic acid as a greenish yellow powder, m.p. $247-49^\circ$. (Found: Equiv., 365.0; Br, 43.5. $C_{13}H_9O_2NBr_2$ requires equiv., 371.0; Br, 43.1%).

The acid chloride crystallised from petroleum ether as a yellow powder, m.p. $118-20^\circ$. (Found: Cl, 9.2; Br, 41.5. $C_{13}H_9ONClBr_2$ requires; Cl, 9.1 Br, 41.1%).

Formation of 2:4-Dibromoacridone.—The reaction was carried out as described above under compound (IV) with $POCl_3$. The product obtained crystallised from glacial acetic acid as a yellowish light powder, m.p. $> 300^\circ$. (Found: Br, 46.1. $C_{13}H_7ONBr_2$ requires Br, 45.3%).

2:4-Dibromo-5-(δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-aminoacridine (I) Dihydrochloride.—To a solution of the chloride of (IV) (0.01 M) in minimum quantity of benzene δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutylamine (0.011 M) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for half an hour. Excess of benzene was removed by distillation at 110° and to the residue $POCl_3$ (25 c.c.) was added, and heating was continued at 110° for 2 hours. Excess of $POCl_3$ was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the cold residual thick liquid was dissolved in a minimum amount of absolute alcohol. The alcoholic extract was filtered and diluted with excess of acetone till the solution became highly turbid, and kept overnight. The yellow solid separating was collected and crystallised from alcohol-acetone mixture as a yellow powder, m.p. $222-26^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 12.2; Br, 27.3. $C_{23}H_{31}ON_3Cl_2Br_2$ requires Cl, 11.9; Br, 26.8%).

Other 5-N-substituted aminoacridine derivatives have been obtained by following the method described above and are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Hydrochloride of 2:4-dibromo-5-substituted acridines.	M.P.*	Found		Mol. formula.	Calc.	
		Br.	Cl.		Br.	Cl.
-5-(7-piperidino-propyl)-amino-7-methoxy-	250-52°	27.9%	12.5%	$C_{22}H_{37}ON_3Cl_2Br_2$	27.6%	12.2%
-5-(δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-amino-	218-20°	28.7	12.7	$C_{22}H_{29}N_3Cl_2Br_2$	28.2	12.5
-5-(7-piperidino-propyl)-amino-	237-40°	29.4	13.1	$C_{21}H_{25}N_3Cl_2Br_2$	29.0	12.9

* With decomposition